

INSTRUMENTAL PERFORMANCE IS AN IMPORTANT ASPECT TO CONSIDER IN THE LEARNING PROCESS. OBSERVATIONAL ANALYSIS OF CHILDREN AND STUDENTS OF CHILDREN'S MUSIC SCHOOLS.

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ABSTRACT

This article is about the process of conducting instrumental lessons of specialized music and art schools, the activities of teachers, skills and abilities, as well as the problems encountered in the process of educating students and practical recommendations for solving them.

Today, Uzbek music can be divided into three main areas. Folk music, folk classical music and compositional music. Popular, vocal, and technical instruments predominate in folklore. Examples include rubab, nay, gijjak, chang, and doyra. It should be noted that the conditions and place of performance in folklore are unique. Therefore, the devices need to be able to adapt and operate quickly in any conditions. To date, Uzbek music is divided into three major areas can be edited. Folk music direction, folk classical music direction and direction of compositional music creation. Popularity in the field of folk oral art feature, sound and more than technically compatible instruments used. Examples include rubab, nay, gijjak, chang, and doyra. Note It should be noted that the

conditions and place of performance in the performance of folk music are unique. The Uzbek classical musical heritage is rich in various instruments and each of them has gone through a long past, a process of structural development and technical improvement is of particular importance. According to the performance criteria, Uzbek folk instruments are two divided into groups. The first group includes all traditional folk instruments. The second group is related to the cultural development of the twentieth century processed instruments. Musical words from traditional folk instruments: tanbur, dutar, sato, rubob, ud, nay, trumpet, neighbor, trumpet, gijjak, chang, law, doyra, drum. Words used in folk art include changqobiz, sibizgi, safoil.

Therefore, the instruments can also adapt quickly and perform in any conditions are required to acquire a receivable feature. Every nation loves its national musical heritage, the tradition of its ancestors if he respects, despises and appreciates it, the art of other nations can also evaluate. After all, the musical traditions that have come down to us are generations is an indication of the strength of the chain. The spiritual wealth of our people in this regard maqoms, classical musical works belonging to the maqom ways to the present day that it maintains a high level of its artistic and aesthetic potential It is worth noting. To study, research and pass them on to future generations delivery is one of the most pressing issues in the demand and need of our time. It is known that the musical culture of the Uzbek people is rich in national instruments tanbur, dutor, gijjak, nay, koshnay, surnay, chang, kanun, ud, rubob, doira and drum-like instruments in the practice of skilled performers with their perfection found a worthy place. Because each instrument has its own history of formation, performance options, has a unique, attractive sound and fans. Rubob, gijjak, dutar and powder on recycled musical instruments The words are repeated according to the criteria of the music soprano, alt, tenor, bass sounds processed samples. A group of drums and percussion instruments consisting of trumpets, horns, drums and doyras formed in the practice of execution from ancient times, of all public events of our people became an active participant. Ensembles of traditional instruments are few properties. Extensive and great sound in the performance larger instruments than the sum of all instruments in order to be able to ensemble was formed. In the practice of

instrumental music performance and status performance and performing in small groups has also become a tradition. Overcoming a lot of help with a music teacher's nap possible. But still, all school students are improvised methods in solving the problem of acquaintance with instrumental music performance the ingenuity of the teacher is not enough. Or, in addition to this sound, in a music class was it possible to appeal to others? Finally, D. B. Kabalevskiy also 50 years to the music science program for secondary schools more time has passed. Indeed, musical instruments glorify the spirituality of humanity in tones is a means of expression, that is, a product of folk art, and has always been among the masses The shape is made by skilled craftsmen and assembled is a miraculous and expressive symbol. The national pride of every nation in the instruments, tradition, people have found their expression, and so is the voice they emit adapted In the modern process, a new look at the traditions of the past is advanced such as adapting from development techniques and nurturing the perfect man special attention is paid to value. After all, music is the most important part of human development An important factor in the spiritual and spiritual upbringing of new people is the child factor considered as Pay attention to this at all stages of the learning process their reason is unquestionable.

Methods of teaching children in music and art schools provide students with basic information about the instrument, the correct position of the instrument (staging) and the gradual acquisition of theoretical knowledge. begins with learning. The entrance exams for a music school test a student's talent, hearing, memory, and

sense of rhythm. Naturally, some students may have lower ability to sense rhythm, while others may have hearing impairments. It is necessary to correct these shortcomings, to develop musical ability. That is, it is advisable to work on more rhythm in the teaching process with a student with a lower ability to sense rhythm. In the classroom, the teacher plays different rhythms through applause and asks the student to repeat this rhythm, which stimulates the gradual development of his ability to feel the rhythm. Of course in this process it is necessary to gradually move from a simple, simple rhythm to a complex one. In the first lesson the student is told about the history of the origin of his instrument, the structure of the instrument, the famous teacher-musicians who performed on this instrument, the importance of the instrument in the learning process, its place in the orchestra. It is expedient to give general concepts. It is important to correctly form the state of

execution (pasanovka) on the instrument. From the first session, special attention should be paid to the correct sitting of the student. Even a small mistake that can occur in a sitting position has a negative effect on a student's low performance skills as well as body development. The main task in this regard is to set the staging, taking into account the height of the student, the length of his arms and legs, when teaching the student to sit properly. That is, it is the important task of this teacher to properly develop each student as a musician, based on their individual situation. Music theory and solfeggio are taught in music schools along with playing the instrument. Perfect mastery of these sciences is important for the performer. Failure to master the theoretical sciences in music has a negative impact on the future knowledge of the performer. The performer is taught step-by-step playing skills on the instrument.

References:

1. Cholg'u ijrochiligi o'quv qo'llanma. O.I. Karimov. Buxoro 2020
2. Cholg'u ijrochiligi. O'quv qo'llanma. Ravshan Abduazimov. Toshkent 2018
3. Xalq cholg'ulari anatologiyasi. A. Tashmatova. Toshkent 2014
4. Ijrochilik san'ati tarixi. A. Tashmatova.
5. Cholg'ushunoslik. Maruza matni. Asqarali Odilov. Samarqand 2012
6. www.ziyo.uz
7. www.wikipedia.uz
8. www.hurshiddavron.kutubhonasi